

Theoretical and numerical modeling of the radical photo-crosslinking process in semi-crystalline polymer networks

Matteo Arricca ^a,* , Lorenzo Bonetti ^a, Massimo Messori ^b, Stefano Pandini ^c,
Giulia Scalet ^a,*

^a Department of Civil Engineering and Architecture, University of Pavia, via Ferrata 3, Pavia 27100, Italy

^b Department of Applied Science and Technology, Politecnico di Torino, Corso Duca degli Abruzzi 24, Torino 10129, Italy

^c Department of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering, University of Brescia, via Branze 38, Brescia 25133, Italy

ARTICLE INFO

Dataset link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20340108>

Keywords:

Radical photo-crosslinking
Semi-crystalline polymer networks
Mass balance equations

ABSTRACT

Radical photo-crosslinking is a widely used strategy for the fabrication of polymer networks, as it enables efficient and spatially-controllable formation of chemically-crosslinked architectures. The performance of photo-crosslinked networks is strongly governed by the efficiency and uniformity of the crosslinking process. Despite its widespread use, only limited theoretical frameworks are available to describe the radical photo-crosslinking process in semi-crystalline polymer networks in a unified and predictive manner.

In this work, we propose a framework to describe light-induced radical crosslinking in semi-crystalline polymer networks. The model combines a three-dimensional formulation of the Beer–Lambert law for radiative transfer with mass balance equations governing photo-initiator activation, radical generation, and crosslinking reactions. Reaction kinetics are described through the law of mass action, finally enabling a quantitative prediction of network evolution as a function of processing parameters.

The framework is validated on poly(ϵ -caprolactone)-based networks, which are widely employed as shape memory polymers. An experimental campaign is conducted in which light intensity, exposure time, and processing temperature are systematically varied. Model predictions are compared against experimentally measured indicators of crosslinking efficiency, demonstrating the capability of the framework to capture the influence of photo-crosslinking conditions on network formation.

The proposed approach provides a novel theoretical tool to rationalize and optimize radical photo-crosslinking in semi-crystalline polymer networks and establishes a foundation for future coupling with thermo-mechanical and shape memory constitutive models, with implications for the design of high-performance polymer systems.

1. Introduction

Radical photo-crosslinking is a widely employed strategy for the fabrication of polymer networks thanks to its versatility, efficiency, and compatibility with advanced manufacturing techniques. By exploiting the activation of photo-initiator molecules under light irradiation, radical photo-crosslinking enables the generation of chemically-crosslinked networks from pre-existing polymer chains, allowing precise spatial and temporal control over network formation. As a result, photo-crosslinked polymer networks are extensively used across a broad range of application domains, including biomedical devices, tissue engineering, soft robotics, and other smart material systems [1,2].

Among the various classes of photo-crosslinked materials, semi-crystalline polymer networks have attracted significant attention. In

these systems, the coexistence of crystalline and amorphous domains, combined with a chemically-crosslinked architecture, enables unique thermo-mechanical properties compared with purely amorphous networks. Semi-crystalline networks fabricated via photo-crosslinking are employed in several contexts, including actuating materials and adaptive structures, where their functional response is tightly linked to the parameters involved in the crosslinking process. A significant example of such applications is their use as shape memory polymers, which has attracted considerable interest [3].

The performance of the resulting material critically depends on the efficiency and uniformity of the crosslinking process [4]. Upon irradiation, light propagates through the material and activates photo-initiators, generating free radicals that interact with polymer chains and trigger crosslinking reactions, ultimately leading to the formation

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: matteo.arricca@unipv.it (M. Arricca), giulia.scalet@unipv.it (G. Scalet).

of a three-dimensional polymer network. Importantly, the physical, mechanical, and functional properties of the resulting materials, such as stiffness, transition temperatures, actuation capability, and long-term stability, are strongly influenced by photo-crosslinking parameters, including light intensity, exposure time, processing temperature, and fabrication technique. Recent experimental studies have demonstrated that these parameters can be exploited to tailor the physico-mechanical, thermal, and shape memory performance of semi-crystalline poly(ϵ -caprolactone) networks, both in conventionally processed and additively manufactured samples [5]. Consequently, understanding and controlling the photo-crosslinking process is of fundamental importance for the rational design and optimization of polymer networks.

From a theoretical standpoint, the interaction between light and polymeric materials has been investigated in a variety of contexts, often addressing different but interconnected phenomena. Light-activated polymers have been extensively studied with reference to light-induced shape memory behavior, macromolecular architecture evolution, and changes in material properties [6–8], as well as photo-degradation phenomena [9]. In parallel, photo-induced polymerization — namely, the formation of polymer networks from monomeric species under light irradiation — has been the subject of decades of investigation, particularly in connection with the rapid development of vat photopolymerization-based additive manufacturing technologies. These studies span from reaction kinetics and radical chemistry [10–12] to the coupling between polymerization processes and mechanical behavior [13–16]. Another used approach is based on molecular dynamics simulations that helped, for instance, in calculating the thermo-physical, mechanical, and shape memory properties for chemically-crosslinked thermoset shape memory polymers after light-curing to form a polymer network [17]. Collectively, these frameworks provide valuable insight into the coupling between light propagation, radical generation, and network evolution.

Although the light-driven processes underlying the aforementioned phenomena are well-known and thoroughly described, only a limited number of contributions have addressed the modeling of radical crosslinking processes within a rigorous theoretical framework. In particular, existing approaches are primarily based on kinetic or semiempirical descriptions. For instance, kinetic models of free-radical crosslinking copolymerization have been proposed [18], while semiempirical and kinetic formulations have been developed for photopolymerization processes, including semi-crystalline systems [19,20]. However, these approaches are typically formulated in a lumped or phenomenological manner and do not provide a unified continuum framework coupling radiative transfer, radical kinetics, and explicit network formation from pre-existing polymer chains.

The present work aims to propose a model capable of describing and characterizing the radical photo-crosslinking process in semi-crystalline polymer networks. The proposed framework is based on the three-dimensional formulation of the Beer–Lambert law to describe radiative transfer within the material, coupled with mass balance equations that account for radical generation and crosslinking reactions. Reaction rates are modeled through the law of mass action, in accordance with standard chemical kinetics.

We apply the proposed general framework to the radical photo-crosslinking of poly(ϵ -caprolactone)-based semi-crystalline polymer networks. The model is eventually validated against an experimental campaign that investigates the efficiency of the photo-crosslinking process in 3D printed samples under different conditions, including varying light intensity, exposure time, and processing temperature.

In recent studies, we have developed theoretical and numerical models — supported by experimental validation — of the shape memory behavior of poly(ϵ -caprolactone)-based semi-crystalline networks [21] and of multi-phase semi-crystalline systems [22], with experimental comparisons against poly(ethylene glycol)/poly(ϵ -caprolactone) copolymer networks [23], fabricated via radical photo-crosslinking. A

thorough understanding and quantitative characterization of the radical photo-crosslinking process in these materials are therefore essential to optimize network formation and maximize material performance.

The manuscript is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the experimental approach, including the material preparation protocol. Section 3 introduces the fundamentals of mass balance equations, whose understanding is essential for characterizing the process under investigation. Section 4 constitutes the theoretical core of the work, where we introduce the photo-chemical events, the radiative transfer modeling, and the crosslinking kinetics that govern the formation of the polymer network. This section also provides the essential definitions and assumptions regarding reaction rate factors, prior to the formulation of the full set of governing mass balance equations. Section 5 deals with the numerical implementation of light and mass balance equations, while Section 6 presents and compares the experimental and numerical results, including a discussion on the identification of model parameters. Section 7 represents an important part of this work, as it provides a critical and constructive discussion of the model, including the adopted assumptions and simplifications, and offers insights into possible future developments aimed at achieving a more realistic description and characterization of the radical photo-crosslinking process, which must necessarily progress in parallel with experimental advances. Finally, Section 8 presents the concluding remarks.

2. Experimental methods

This section presents the investigated semi-crystalline network, the fabrication process, the crosslinking procedure and parameters, and the experimental tests conducted to obtain the data necessary for both the calibration and validation of the theoretical model.

2.1. Material

Poly(ϵ -caprolactone) diol (α , ω -hydroxyl-terminated poly(ϵ -caprolactone), $M_n = 10$ kDa), 2-isocyanatoethyl methacrylate (2-IEM, 98%), tetrahydrofuran (THF) and 2-hydroxy-2-methylpropiophenone (ADDITOL HDMAP) were purchased from Merck and used without any further purification step. Methacrylated poly(ϵ -caprolactone) was obtained according to a previous protocol [24]. Briefly, poly(ϵ -caprolactone) diol and 2-IEM were reacted in a glass flask at a 1:2.4 molar ratio. Methacrylation was carried out at 100 °C for 3–4 h under stirring and a nitrogen atmosphere, and reaction progress was monitored by FT-IR spectroscopy. Dynamic vacuum was then applied to remove unreacted 2-IEM, confirmed by FT-IR spectroscopy. The resulting methacrylated poly(ϵ -caprolactone) was stored in the dark at room temperature (RT) until use. Further details on synthesis and characterization are reported in Ref. [24].

2.2. Sample fabrication

Computer-aided design (CAD) models with dimensions of $30 \times 5 \times 0.41$ mm were drawn using Autodesk Fusion (v. 2605.1.18), converted into .stl files, and imported into DNA Studio software (v. 4) for printing. Methacrylated poly(ϵ -caprolactone) was melt-mixed (80 °C, 100 rpm, 30 min) with the radical photo-initiator (ADDITOL HDMAP, 0.5 wt%). After cooling, the mix was grinded and loaded in the cartridge of a thermoplastic printhead of the pneumatic bioprinter (Cellink BioX6). Fabrication was achieved according to a previously established protocol [25]. Briefly, the thermoplastic printhead was equipped with a 22 G nozzle (0.41 mm diameter) and heated to 70 °C. Printing was achieved at a pressure of 15–20 kPa and a speed of 10 mm/s, employing a concentric infill pattern with 98% density. Radical photo-crosslinking was achieved using the printer's integrated UV module ($\lambda = 365$ nm), irradiating each printed layer after fabrication. Three photo-crosslinking parameters were controlled: (i) the print bed temperature (T_{XL}), set at 20 °C or 60 °C; (ii) the UV light intensity (I_{XL}), set at 0.5 mW/cm² or 6 mW/cm²; (iii) the exposure time (t_{XL}), set at selected values between 2 and 300 s. The resulting 3D specimens were used for subsequent characterization.

2.3. Sample characterization: gel fraction tests

The gel fraction was assumed to be a physically-meaningful and easily-measurable quantity representative of the degree of crosslinking achieved in the specimen. Accordingly, gel fraction tests were carried out on the 3D printed specimens ($n = 3$ for each photo-crosslinking condition). The samples were weighted after fabrication (m_0), then immersed in THF at RT for 24 h (immersion ratio = 0.5 g poly(ϵ -caprolactone): 15 mL THF). After 24 h, the swollen specimens were recovered from the solvent and dried at RT for 24 h. The dry specimens were then weighted (m_d), and the gel fraction (G_F^{exp} (%)) was calculated using the following equation [25]:

$$G_F^{\text{exp}}(\%) = \frac{m_d}{m_0} \times 100. \quad (1)$$

2.4. Mass densities and molar concentrations

For the sake of notation simplicity and consistency throughout the manuscript, we denote chemical species by upright capital letters, and molar concentrations (in moles per unit volume) by the same capital letter in *italics* (omitting the standard use of square brackets).

Let PH denote the photo-initiator molecule (ADDITOL HDMA), and PCL the macromolecular polymer chains (methacrylated poly(ϵ -caprolactone)). The mass densities of PH and PCL are given by

$$\bar{\rho}_{\text{PH}} = \frac{m_{\text{PH}}}{V_{\text{PH}}} = 1.077 \text{ g cm}^{-3}, \quad \bar{\rho}_{\text{PCL}} = \frac{m_{\text{PCL}}}{V_{\text{PCL}}} = 1.146 \text{ g cm}^{-3}, \quad (2)$$

where m_{PH} and m_{PCL} denote the masses, and V_{PH} and V_{PCL} the corresponding volumes, of PH and PCL, respectively.

The samples were prepared by mixing 10 g of PCL with 0.5 g of ADDITOL HDMA. Accordingly, $m_{\text{PCL}} = 10 \text{ g}$ and $m_{\text{PH}} = 0.5 \text{ g}$. Based on Eqs. (2), the total sample volume is

$$V = V_{\text{PH}} + V_{\text{PCL}} = 9.19 \text{ cm}^3, \quad (3)$$

with $V_{\text{PH}} = m_{\text{PH}} \bar{\rho}_{\text{PH}}^{-1}$ and $V_{\text{PCL}} = m_{\text{PCL}} \bar{\rho}_{\text{PCL}}^{-1}$.

Given V , considering the molar mass of PH, $\kappa_{\text{PH}} = 164.2 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$, and the number-average molar mass of PCL, $\kappa_{\text{PCL}} = 10^4 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$, the two chemical species are present within the sample with mass densities

$$\rho_{\text{PH}} = \frac{m_{\text{PH}}}{V} = 0.054 \text{ g cm}^{-3}, \quad \rho_{\text{PCL}} = \frac{m_{\text{PCL}}}{V} = 1.088 \text{ g cm}^{-3}, \quad (4)$$

and molar concentrations

$$PH = \frac{\rho_{\text{PH}}}{\kappa_{\text{PH}}} = 33.13 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ mol cm}^{-3}, \quad PCL = \frac{\rho_{\text{PCL}}}{\kappa_{\text{PCL}}} = 10.88 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ mol cm}^{-3}. \quad (5)$$

3. Preliminaries on mass balance equations

Consider an ideal system containing n chemical species amongst which r chemical reactions are possible. From a macroscopic point of view it is sufficient to assume that at most $n - 1$ independent chemical reactions occur in the system [26], which means that $r \leq n - 1$.

It is customary to discuss chemical reactions that proceed at constant volume in terms of molar concentrations [26].

For a generic chemical species C , its mass balance equation can be formulated as

$$\frac{d}{dt} C(\mathbf{X}, t) = \sum_{j=1}^r \bar{\nu}_{C,j} \bar{J}_j(\mathbf{X}, t) - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{H}_C(\mathbf{X}, t) \quad (6)$$

at a point \mathbf{X} and time t . Symbol d/dt denotes the material time-derivative; $\bar{\nu}_{C,j}$ is the true stoichiometric coefficient of species C involved into the j -th chemical reaction, which will be positive (negative) if C is a product (reactant); vector \mathbf{H}_C represents the mass flux; ∇ is the nabla operator; “ \cdot ” denotes the scalar product.

For ideal systems one assumes in chemical kinetics that the law of mass action holds, and the reaction rate can be modeled according to its conventional description using molar concentrations and true stoichiometric coefficients [26]. For a generic j -th independent chemical reaction, it holds that

$$\bar{J}_j(\mathbf{X}, t) = k_f \prod_{i=1}^q C_i^{-\bar{\nu}_i}(\mathbf{X}, t) - k_r \prod_{i=q+1}^n C_i^{\bar{\nu}_i}(\mathbf{X}, t), \quad (7)$$

with C_i molar concentration of reactants for $i = 1, \dots, q$, and of products for $i = q + 1, \dots, n$, k_f positive rate constant for the forward reaction, yielding products, and k_r positive rate constant for the reverse reaction, yielding reactants.

Lastly, the mass flux vector, \mathbf{H}_C , is commonly modeled by the Fick's law, which can be written as

$$\mathbf{H}_C(\mathbf{X}, t) = -\mathbb{D}_C \nabla C(\mathbf{X}, t), \quad (8)$$

with \mathbb{D}_C positive fourth-order diffusion tensor of species C .

In the following, the functional dependence on space and time is omitted for readability and specified only when necessary.

4. Theoretical formulation

Based on the theoretical treatment of the mass balance equations presented in Section 3, we here introduce the governing equations to model the radical photo-crosslinking process in semi-crystalline polymer networks. Although the formulation is general (see the discussion on model applicability in Section 7), it is here specialized to the material system investigated in this work and described in Section 2.

4.1. Material system description

Consider a semi-crystalline network made of one semi-crystalline polymer. The polymer can be simply described as composed of one crystalline domain and one amorphous domain, whose fraction may change upon temperature variations. Particularly, for the polymer, it is possible to define and measure the temperatures of crystallization and melting (respectively, T_c and T_m), which well define the internal architecture of the material in terms of phase contents. For temperatures higher than T_m , the network consists of the amorphous polymer chains, chemically connected by crosslinks. Below T_c , the network is made of crystallites, connected by the amorphous chemically-crosslinked domain.

Chemical crosslinks are established via radical photo-crosslinking among the amorphous polymer chains. Upon irradiation, UV light propagates through the material and activates the photo-initiators, generating free radicals that interact with polymer chains and trigger the crosslinking reactions, ultimately leading to the formation of a three-dimensional polymer network.

In our case the polymer is poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (see details on material preparation in Section 2). Accordingly, the semi-crystalline network was obtained by crosslinking reactions starting from methacrylate-terminated poly(ϵ -caprolactone). The latter was crosslinked via UV irradiation in the presence of the radical photo-initiator ADDITOL HDMA.

Based on this material description and the investigated material, we consider a system that, at the initial time $t = 0$, contains photo-initiator molecules, denoted as PH, and free inactive polymer chains, indicated as PCL, with spatially homogeneous molar concentrations PH and PCL , respectively (Fig. 1). Here, the term ‘free inactive’ indicates methacrylate-terminated poly(ϵ -caprolactone) whose methacrylic end groups have still to react. We highlight that each end (also referred to as ‘terminal’ in the following) has functionality equal to two (also referred to as ‘sites’ in the following), meaning that it can react twice.

In the following, we aim to describe the photo-crosslinking process of this material system. Moreover, we will analyze the effect of UV light intensity, exposure time, and processing temperature. It is already clear

Fig. 1. Simplified representation of a free inactive polymer chain, PCL, and a photo-initiator molecule, PH, adopted in the present work.

here that the processing temperature will affect the material state. As anticipated in Section 2.3, the degree of crosslinking achieved will be quantified in terms of the gel fraction which is a physically-meaningful and easily-measurable quantity, useful for model validation purposes.

4.2. Photo-chemistry

Light propagation through the system induces a sequence of photo-chemical events that lead to the formation of the three-dimensional polymer network.

Initially, photons interact with the embedded photo-initiator molecules, PH, which chemically disassociate into two active free radicals, R[•]. Such process can be described via the following chemical reaction

where $k^{(9)}$ denotes the photo-initiation rate factor, defined as

$$k^{(9)}(X, t) = k_{\text{ph}}(X, t) = \tilde{k}_{\text{ph}} I(X, t), \quad (10a)$$

with $I(X, t)$ being the local light intensity. The proportionality constant \tilde{k}_{ph} is expressed as [6]

$$\tilde{k}_{\text{ph}} = \frac{\alpha_{\text{PH}} \phi_{\text{PH}}}{N_A h \nu}, \quad (10b)$$

where α_{PH} is the molar absorption coefficient, ϕ_{PH} is the quantum efficiency (accounting for the fact that not all absorbed photons lead to photo-cleavage events), N_A is the Avogadro's number, h is the Planck's constant, and $\nu = c \lambda^{-1}$ is the monochromatic light frequency, with c the speed of light and λ the wavelength.

Then, radical species may undergo inactivation for several reasons, e.g., through mutual interactions, by reacting with oxygen present in the system, or simply over time if they do not find a site for chemical interaction. For the sake of simplicity, and in the absence of experimental evidences, we encompass all the aforementioned processes within the following one-way termination reaction

where $k^{(11)} = k_t$ is the positive termination rate constant and R is the inactive moiety after radical addition. Here, the term 'inactive' denotes a radical that has lost its activity. Note that k_t may be reasonably considered a function of temperature, since all processes affecting reaction (11) can vary with temperature. For a spatially and temporally uniform temperature distribution within the sample, k_t is constant throughout the domain; accordingly,

$$k_t = k_t(T). \quad (12)$$

It is of fundamental importance to clarify at the outset that the radical concentration field is commonly restricted to the range [11]

$$10^{-6} \text{ mol m}^{-3} \leq \text{R}^{\bullet} \leq 10^{-4} \text{ mol m}^{-3}. \quad (13)$$

Such an extremely low molar concentration has several crucial consequences that must be taken into account, including an exceptionally high termination coefficient, k_t , which ensures that R[•] remains within

Fig. 2. Simplified representation of the chain activation process, illustrating the reaction between a free inactive chain, PCL, and an active radical molecule, R[•]. R[•] breaks the double covalent bond ((CH₃)C = CH₂) and activates that end of the chain. The radical activity is transferred to the C(CH₃) site — represented by the light grey bullet — of the newly formed active chain, PCL[•]. The black bullet in PCL[•] indicates that the terminal is free and active, while the white bullet denotes an inactive moiety after radical addition.

the range specified above, as well as, the possibility of introducing reasonable simplifications in the model, as will be clarified hereinafter.

When an active radical R[•] encounters an end of the inactive PCL chain, it breaks the double covalent bond ((CH₃)C = CH₂) and activates that end of the chain, thereby producing a polymer chain with one active end and one inactive end, denoted by PCL[•]. This process is schematically depicted in Fig. 2 and can be modeled via the following chemical reaction

with $k^{(14)} = k_a$ the activation rate factor. It would be reasonable to assume that k_a varies in space and time as a function of availability of chain sites for activation by radicals and their progressive depletion. However, in view of condition (13), the depletion of PCL associated with the production of PCL[•] via reaction (14) is not expected to be significant. Therefore, to avoid unnecessary complications, we assume k_a to be independent of space and time. Nevertheless, since temperature may still indirectly influence chain activation through its effect on chain mobility, we state

$$k_a = k_a(T). \quad (15)$$

Superscript “⁽¹⁴⁾” is adopted to indicate the *active state* of a chemical species. Active radicals are produced through the chemical reaction (9), whereas the termination reaction (11) removes this activity from previously active radical molecules. Similarly, in the activation reaction (14), the activity carried by R[•] is transferred to the polymer chain, yielding PCL[•]. The same convention will be applied throughout the rest of the manuscript.

All chemical reactions introduced in this section are considered only in their forward direction. While it is evident that radical molecules dissociating from photo-initiators, according to reaction (9), cannot revert to form photo-initiators, and that terminated radicals in reaction (11) cannot regain their activity, a brief clarification is required regarding reaction (14). Specifically, for the sake of simplicity, we assume that once a chain-end site is activated by a radical, it does not lose its activity, regardless of the passage of time or the occurrence of other chemical events.

4.2.1. Light propagation

With the aim of determining the light intensity that activates the photo-crosslinking process (see also Eq. (10a)), we need to model light propagation through the material. For the sake of simplicity, we assume that the material is structurally and chemically homogeneous without internal boundaries, i.e., scattering events arise only from exterior

boundaries, and thus are ignored [6,27]. Accordingly, we consider the following three-dimensional version of the Beer–Lambert law [27]

$$\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{X}, t) \cdot \nabla I(\mathbf{X}, t) + \sigma(\mathbf{X}, t) I(\mathbf{X}, t) = 0 \quad \text{in } B, \quad (16a)$$

$$I(\mathbf{X}, t) = \bar{I}_0 \quad \text{on } \partial B, \quad (16b)$$

where B denotes the body volume, ∂B its boundary surface, and \bar{I}_0 the spatially homogeneous light intensity applied at time $t = 0$. The vector \mathbf{Q} and the scalar σ represent the direction of the light and the extinction field, respectively. The direction field is often uniform in space and time, yielding $\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{X}, t) = \mathbf{Q}$. The extinction field σ characterizes the spatial and time depletion rate of the intensity field. Since photo-initiators, free radicals, and polymer chains can all absorb photons, attenuating light as it propagates through the material, it can be modeled as [6]

$$\sigma = \alpha_{\text{PH}} PH + \alpha_{\text{R}} \cdot R^* + \alpha_{\text{PCL}} PCL, \quad (17)$$

where, for each species $C = \text{PH}, R^*, \text{PCL}$, α_C is the molar absorptivity coefficient and C is its molar concentration.

According to condition (13), the contribution of radicals to light attenuation is negligible. Moreover, molten PCL homopolymer contains no chromophoric groups, and therefore relatively low absorption values are expected. The same is likely true for methacrylate-terminated poly(ϵ -caprolactone), which is not expected to exhibit significant absorption at $\lambda=365$ nm. Therefore, the extinction field (17) can be approximated as

$$\sigma \simeq \alpha_{\text{PH}} PH. \quad (18)$$

A more detailed discussion on the adopted model simplifications is provided in Section 7.

4.3. Crosslinking chemistry

In the following, we introduce the chemical reactions responsible for the formation of the crosslinked polymer network. The rate factors appearing in these reactions will be discussed in Section 4.4. We emphasize that the reactions reported below are not expressed using standard chemical notation; rather, they are formulated specifically for modeling purposes, with the aim of capturing the underlying reaction mechanisms in a form suitable for the analysis of the different involved chemical species.

To avoid redundancy, we first clarify the concept of the activity associated with an active radical R^* . As discussed in connection with the activation reaction (14), this activity enables the cleavage of a double covalent bond at a chain end, saturating one site while activating the other site on the same chain. The same mechanism occurs when an active chain-end site reacts with an inactive end of another chain. Importantly, this activity — originating from a previously active radical — does not vanish; rather, it is transferred from one chain site to another, continuously breaking double bonds, saturating one site, and activating the next.

We further note that, as with the reactions introduced in Section 4.2, all reactions considered here are treated as irreversible. This assumption implies that, once a crosslinking site is formed, it cannot be broken, and chain detachment is not allowed. For clarity, all chemical reactions described here are schematically illustrated in Fig. 3.

As shown in Fig. 3(a), PCL^* , having one active end, can interact with one of the two inactive terminals of a different PCL, yielding two crosslinked chains — one with a crosslinked saturated end (PCL_{\ddagger}^*) and one with a crosslinked active end (PCL_{\ddagger}^*) — while both possess a free inactive end on the opposite side. The process can be represented by the following chemical reaction

where PCL is converted into PCL_{\ddagger}^* and PCL^* into PCL_{\ddagger}^* . PCL_{\ddagger}^* represents a polymer chain with one crosslinked saturated end denoted

by the symbol \ddagger , indicating that this terminal has both sites no-longer available for further reactions. PCL_{\ddagger}^* represents a polymer chain with one crosslinked active end denoted by \ddagger^* , implying that this terminal is crosslinked at one site and reactive at the other (having received the activity from PCL^*). For both species, the opposite end remains free and inactive; being free, we define chains of the type PCL_{\ddagger}^* and PCL_{\ddagger}^* as *pendant* chains.

Crosslinked chains of the type PCL_{\ddagger}^* , possessing one crosslinked active end, can interact with one of the free inactive ends of PCL, as depicted in Fig. 3(b),

yielding the same products as reaction (19), namely PCL_{\ddagger}^* and PCL_{\ddagger}^* , obtained from PCL_{\ddagger}^* and PCL, respectively. It is worth noting that, since the activity is transferred from one site to another, reaction (20) may proceed continuously, leading to the formation of isolated crosslinked structures within the system, as schematically illustrated in Fig. 4.

The free inactive end of a crosslinked chain PCL_{\ddagger}^* can also react with PCL_{\ddagger}^* , as reported in Fig. 3(c),

yielding PCL_{\ddagger}^* from PCL_{\ddagger}^* , while the reactant PCL_{\ddagger}^* produces PCL_{\ddagger}^* . The latter represents a chain crosslinked at both ends — one being saturated (\ddagger) and the other still possessing one reactive site (\ddagger^*). We will refer to PCL_{\ddagger}^* as double crosslinked chain.

Furthermore, PCL_{\ddagger}^* chains can also react with each other through the active site of one chain terminal and the inactive one of the other, according to

where the chain that yields the activity is turned into PCL_{\ddagger}^* , whereas the chain receiving the activity transforms into PCL_{\ddagger}^* , a chain in which both ends are crosslinked at one site and reactive at the other. Also PCL_{\ddagger}^* will be referred to as double crosslinked chain. This process is represented in Fig. 3(d).

As shown in Fig. 3(e), polymer chains PCL_{\ddagger}^* can react, through the active site of their crosslinked end, with one of the free inactive ends of PCL

where PCL receives the activity and is transformed into PCL_{\ddagger}^* , while PCL_{\ddagger}^* , having exhausted its activity, saturates its remaining reactive site and becomes PCL_{\ddagger}^* . The latter thus represents a double crosslinked chain.

Chains PCL_{\ddagger}^* can further interact with the inactive end of PCL_{\ddagger}^* , as illustrated in Fig. 3(f), yielding

where PCL_{\ddagger}^* , upon receiving the activity, is converted to PCL_{\ddagger}^* , while PCL_{\ddagger}^* produces PCL_{\ddagger}^* , similarly as before.

Furthermore, as shown in Fig. 3(g), the inactive terminal of PCL_{\ddagger}^* can interact with the remaining active site of PCL_{\ddagger}^* , according to

in which PCL_{\ddagger}^* produces PCL_{\ddagger}^* , through activation of the remaining reactive site, while PCL_{\ddagger}^* is formed from the original PCL_{\ddagger}^* chain.

A chain of type PCL_{\ddagger}^* can also interact, through one of its active sites, with one of the free inactive ends of PCL, as depicted in Fig. 3(h),

where PCL and PCL_{\ddagger}^* are converted into PCL_{\ddagger}^* and PCL_{\ddagger}^* , respectively.

Fig. 3. Simplified representation of all crosslinking chemical reactions derived in the present work.

Similarly, PCL_r^+ may react with the remaining inactive terminal of a PCL_z chain, as shown in Fig. 3(i),

and with the inactive terminal of PCL_r , as Fig. 3(j) illustrates,

in which PCL_r becomes PCL_r^+ through activation of its previously inactive terminal, whereas PCL_r^+ produces PCL_z .

Lastly, according to the crosslinking chemistry described in this section, the crosslinked network is expected to exhibit a structure resembling the simplified one schematically represented in Fig. 5.

Remark. Note that, in order to simplify the proposed model and in light of condition (13), several theoretically possible chemical interactions have been neglected. First, since the radical concentration field is of significantly small magnitude, we have disregarded the possibility that two radicals simultaneously interact with both inactive ends of PCL. Accounting for this would have required defining a new species, i.e., a chain with both terminals active, and accounting for all the corresponding reactions. Similarly, radicals interacting with the inactive terminal of a chain already crosslinked at the opposite end (as in PCL_z and PCL_r) have also been neglected.

It is also worth noting that, strictly speaking, the product PCL_z of reaction (19), produced from PCL^* , is not identical to the PCL_z species generated in reactions (20), (21), and (22). While the latter

Fig. 4. Depiction of a crosslinked structure composed solely of pendant chains generated by chemical reaction (20).

Fig. 5. Example of simplified representation of a part of a crosslinked PCL network.

are linked to two chains at the same terminal, the former is bonded to only one, the other side being occupied by the radical involved in the activation reaction (14). Nevertheless, given condition (13) and the resulting extremely low concentration of PCL^{\cdot} , this distinction is negligible, and all PCL_{\ddagger}^{\cdot} chains are therefore treated as having two other chains linked at one terminal.

Lastly, we do not claim the complete absence of the neglected species or reactions — they may indeed occur within the complex photo-chemical process considered. However, their influence is expected to be negligible compared with the dominant mechanisms discussed in this section, allowing for a simplified yet physically-consistent description of the photo-crosslinking process.

4.3.1. Rate factors of crosslinking reactions

The chemical reactions reported above contain rate factors denoted with the letter $k^{(i)}$, being i the equation number defining the specific reaction. Chemical reactions involving one free inactive chain, PCL , among their reactants (Eqs. (19), (20), (23) and (26)) are associated with a forward rate factor denoted by k_{xl} and referred to as the crosslinking rate factor. Reactions between crosslinked chains of any type (Eqs. (21), (22), (24), (25), (27), and (28)) are associated with a forward rate factor defined, for simplicity, as the double crosslinking rate factor, denoted by k_{xl}^{xl} .

It would be reasonable to assume that both the crosslinking and double crosslinking rate factors vary in space and time, i.e., $k_{xl} = k_{xl}(X, t)$ and $k_{xl}^{xl} = k_{xl}^{xl}(X, t)$.

The former is the only primary parameter influencing the gel fraction (denoted with letter G_F), as discussed in detail in Section 4.6. Since experimental evidences presented in Section 6 clearly show that G_F is also temperature-dependent, we can write $G_F = G_F(X, t, T(X, t))$. Therefore, even in experiments performed under uniform temperature, k_{xl} cannot be considered constant, as G_F itself varies. Accordingly, we define k_{xl} according to the following function

$$k_{xl}(X, t, T) = \bar{k}_{xl}(T) \left(1 - \frac{G_F^{P(T)}(X, t, T)}{G_F^{\max}(T)} \right)^{Q(T)}, \quad (29)$$

where $\bar{k}_{xl}(T)$ is constant in space and time under uniform temperature conditions, $G_F^{\max}(T)$ denotes the saturation limit of the gel fraction,

measured experimentally for each test case, $P(T)$ and $Q(T)$ are model parameters.

In the absence of additional experimental evidences, the rate factors of the crosslinking reactions (19), (20), (23), and (26) are estimated using a simplified, physically-motivated rationale based on polymer chain mobility and their approximate likelihood of interaction (a discussion of more physically-based methods is provided in Section 7). Consider reaction (19), in which both PCL and PCL^{\cdot} chains, as well as their terminal ends, are freely mobile. Accordingly, the probability of a successful reaction is governed by the ability of the active site of PCL^{\cdot} to move toward one of the two inactive ends of PCL , or vice versa — thus representing an approximately four-way directional possibility. We assign to reaction (19) the rate factor $k_{xl}(T)$ defined in Eq. (29). Next, consider that crosslinked terminals — whether active or inactive — exhibit negligible mobility, or, at most, are sufficiently sluggish to be regarded as effectively immobile. Consequently, reaction (20) is successful only if one of the two inactive ends of PCL moves toward $PCL_{\ddagger}^{\cdot+}$, yielding an approximately two-way directional possibility. The same reasoning applies to reaction (23), regardless of the fact that the reacting species $PCL_{\ddagger}^{\cdot+}$ has both terminals crosslinked, with only one of them bearing an active site. In this case, the reaction succeeds if one of the two inactive ends of PCL moves toward $PCL_{\ddagger}^{\cdot+}$, again resulting in an approximately two-way directional possibility. Finally, in reaction (26), one of the inactive terminals of PCL may interact with either of the two active sites of $PCL_{\ddagger}^{\cdot+}$, leading to an approximately four-way directional possibility — likely distinct from that associated with reaction (19). For the reasons discussed above, we set

$$k^{(19)} = k_{xl}, \quad k^{(20)} = \alpha k_{xl}, \quad k^{(23)} = \alpha k_{xl}, \quad k^{(26)} = \gamma k_{xl}, \quad (30)$$

with $k_{xl} = k_{xl}(T)$ given by Eq. (29), $\alpha \simeq 0.5$ and $\gamma \leq 1$ model parameters acting as proportionality coefficients.

Now, consider the double crosslinking rate factor. Since the validation of the proposed model relies on the currently available experimental data for the gel fraction, it is important to note that k_{xl}^{xl} has no direct relation to G_F . Indeed, the gel fraction accounts for all polymer chains that are crosslinked, even if only at one terminal. Consequently, a pendant chain that becomes double crosslinked does not affect the value of G_F . Therefore, in order to simplify the proposed model and reduce both the number of parameters and unnecessary complexities, we define, analogously to the rate factors (12) and (15),

$$k_{xl}^{xl} = k_{xl}^{xl}(T), \quad (31)$$

which is therefore constant for experiments performed at uniform temperature in space and time.

Following the reasoning previously adopted, we now estimate the rate factors for reactions (21), (22), (24), (25), (27), and (28). As done previously, we use the first of these reactions to define k_{xl}^{xl} and assign proportionality coefficients to the others based on it. The success of reaction (21) depends solely on the movement of the free end of PCL_{\ddagger}^{\cdot} toward the immobile crosslinked active site of $PCL_{\ddagger}^{\cdot+}$. Accordingly, we set $k^{(21)} = k_{xl}^{xl}$, which represents a one-way directional possibility. The same applies to the rate factors of reactions (24) and (25). Conversely, the success of reaction (22) depends on the mobility of one of the free inactive ends of $PCL_{\ddagger}^{\cdot+}$, which must interact with an immobile crosslinked active site of another $PCL_{\ddagger}^{\cdot+}$, thus defining a two-way directional possibility. Finally, the success of reactions (27) and (28) is also associated with a two-way directional possibility, likely smaller than the one just described, as these involve the interaction between an immobile crosslinked active site of $PCL_{\ddagger}^{\cdot+}$ and the mobile inactive terminal of PCL_{\ddagger}^{\cdot} and $PCL_{\ddagger}^{\cdot+}$, respectively. Accordingly, we set

$$k^{(21)} = k^{(24)} = k^{(25)} = k_{xl}^{xl}, \quad k^{(22)} = \beta k_{xl}^{xl}, \quad k^{(27)} = k^{(28)} = \delta k_{xl}^{xl}, \quad (32)$$

with $k_{xl}^{xl} = k_{xl}^{xl}(T)$, as defined in Eq. (31), $\beta \simeq 2$ and $\gamma \leq \beta$ model parameters acting as proportionality coefficients.

4.4. Reaction rates of chemical reactions

According to the law of mass action (7), considering that all previously introduced chemical reactions are treated only in their forward direction, and taking into account the specifications for the reaction rate factors provided in Sections 4.2 and 4.3.1, the reaction rates of reactions (9), (11), (14), and (19)–(28) write as

$$\bar{J}^{(9)} = k_{\text{ph}} I P H, \quad (33a)$$

$$\bar{J}^{(11)} = k_{\text{r}} R^*, \quad (33b)$$

$$\bar{J}^{(14)} = k_{\text{a}} R^* P C L, \quad (33c)$$

$$\bar{J}^{(19)} = k_{\text{xl}} P C L P C L^*, \quad (33d)$$

$$\bar{J}^{(20)} = \alpha k_{\text{xl}} P C L P C L_{\ddagger}^*, \quad (33e)$$

$$\bar{J}^{(21)} = k_{\text{xl}}^{\text{xl}} P C L_{\ddagger} P C L_{\ddagger}^*, \quad (33f)$$

$$\bar{J}^{(22)} = \beta k_{\text{xl}}^{\text{xl}} P C L_{\ddagger}^* P C L_{\ddagger}^*, \quad (33g)$$

$$\bar{J}^{(23)} = \alpha k_{\text{xl}} P C L P C L_{\ddagger}^*, \quad (33h)$$

$$\bar{J}^{(24)} = k_{\text{xl}}^{\text{xl}} P C L_{\ddagger} P C L_{\ddagger}^*, \quad (33i)$$

$$\bar{J}^{(25)} = k_{\text{xl}}^{\text{xl}} P C L_{\ddagger}^* P C L_{\ddagger}^*, \quad (33j)$$

$$\bar{J}^{(26)} = \gamma k_{\text{xl}} P C L P C L_{\ddagger}^*, \quad (33k)$$

$$\bar{J}^{(27)} = \delta k_{\text{xl}}^{\text{xl}} P C L_{\ddagger} P C L_{\ddagger}^*, \quad (33l)$$

$$\bar{J}^{(28)} = \delta k_{\text{xl}}^{\text{xl}} P C L_{\ddagger}^* P C L_{\ddagger}^*. \quad (33m)$$

4.5. Specifications of mass balance equations

Photo-initiators and radicals are diffusive molecules. Therefore, considering the mass balance equation (6) together with the specifications for the reaction rates (7) and the assumed Fickian diffusion (8), and in accordance with the photo-chemical events introduced in Section 4.2, their mass balances read

$$\frac{d}{dt} P H = -\bar{J}^{(9)} + \mathbb{D}_{\text{PH}} \nabla^2 P H, \quad (34a)$$

and

$$\frac{d}{dt} R^* = 2\bar{J}^{(9)} - \bar{J}^{(11)} - \bar{J}^{(14)} + \mathbb{D}_{\text{R}^*} \nabla^2 R^*, \quad (34b)$$

with \mathbb{D}_{PH} and \mathbb{D}_{R^*} fourth-order diffusion tensors for PH and R^* , respectively. In the numerical tests presented in Section 6, the diffusivity of photo-initiators and radicals is neglected.

Within the system, free polymer chains PCL and PCL^* exhibit classical chain mobility but vanishingly small diffusivity. Accordingly, their mass balance equations are governed solely by the reaction rates. Considering chemical reactions (14), (19), (20), (23) and (26), it follows that

$$\frac{d}{dt} P C L = -\bar{J}^{(14)} - \bar{J}^{(19)} - \bar{J}^{(20)} - \bar{J}^{(23)} - \bar{J}^{(26)}, \quad (34c)$$

and

$$\frac{d}{dt} P C L^* = \bar{J}^{(14)} - \bar{J}^{(19)}. \quad (34d)$$

Since free chains are not diffusive species, the same holds for all types of crosslinked chains. Accordingly, based on the crosslinking chemistry introduced in Section 4.3, the mass balance equations for pendant crosslinked chains read

$$\frac{d}{dt} P C L_{\ddagger}^* = \bar{J}^{(19)} + \bar{J}^{(20)} + \bar{J}^{(22)} - \bar{J}^{(24)} - \bar{J}^{(27)}, \quad (34e)$$

and

$$\frac{d}{dt} P C L_{\ddagger} = \bar{J}^{(19)} - \bar{J}^{(21)} - 2\bar{J}^{(22)} + \bar{J}^{(23)} - \bar{J}^{(25)} + \bar{J}^{(26)} - \bar{J}^{(28)}, \quad (34f)$$

whereas those for double crosslinked chains read

$$\frac{d}{dt} P C L_{\ddagger}^{**} = \bar{J}^{(22)} + \bar{J}^{(25)} - \bar{J}^{(26)} - \bar{J}^{(27)}, \quad (34g)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} P C L_{\ddagger}^{**} = \bar{J}^{(21)} - \bar{J}^{(23)} - \bar{J}^{(25)} + \bar{J}^{(26)} + 2\bar{J}^{(27)} + \bar{J}^{(28)}, \quad (34h)$$

and

$$\frac{d}{dt} P C L_{\ddagger}^{\ddagger} = \bar{J}^{(23)} + \bar{J}^{(24)} + \bar{J}^{(25)}. \quad (34i)$$

4.6. Evaluation of the gel fraction

In order to numerically evaluate the gel fraction for comparison with experimental measurements (1), we first denote by XL the set of all crosslinked chains within the system — both single and double crosslinked — and by XL their molar concentration. Accordingly, it holds that

$$X L = P C L_{\ddagger} + P C L_{\ddagger}^* + P C L_{\ddagger}^{**} + P C L_{\ddagger}^{\ddagger} + P C L_{\ddagger}^{\ddagger}, \quad (35)$$

Its mass balance equation is obtained as the sum of mass balances (34e)–(34i), yielding

$$\frac{d}{dt} X L = 2\bar{J}^{(19)} + \bar{J}^{(20)} + \bar{J}^{(23)} + \bar{J}^{(26)}. \quad (36)$$

As noted in Section 4.3.1, when introducing the rate factor $k_{\text{xl}}^{\text{xl}}$, Eq. (36) clarifies that when a pendant chain becomes a double crosslinked chain, the gel fraction remains unchanged. In fact, the mass balance (36) depends solely on the reaction rates of single crosslinking processes.

Assuming that the molar mass of crosslinked chains is equal to that of free inactive chains, $\kappa_{\text{XL}} = \kappa_{\text{PCL}}$ (see Section 2.4), the gel fraction can be conveniently re-written as

$$\mathcal{G}_{\text{F}}(X, t) = \frac{X L(X, t)}{P C L(X, 0)}, \quad (37)$$

where $P C L(X, 0)$ is the molar concentration of PCL chains at time $t = 0$, given by Eq. (5)₂, while $X L(X, t)$ is evaluated from its mass balance equation (36).

5. Numerical implementation

The model introduced in Section 4 is implemented within a finite element (FE) framework. The FE implementation of model equations and of all the numerical examples presented in Section 6 is carried out using the symbolic code generation system AceGen/AceFEM within Wolfram Mathematica.

5.1. Weak form of the Beer–Lambert law and discretization

We first derive the weak form for the governing equations (16) and then we discretize the governing integral equation.

Following standard arguments, we multiply Eq. (16a) by the weighting function w and integrate over the domain

$$\int_B w \boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \nabla I \, dV + \int_B w \sigma I \, dV = 0 \quad (38)$$

which must hold for any w .

Then, the body is discretized by means of finite elements such that $B = \bigcup B^e$. The light intensity field is interpolated inside each element by

$$I(X, t) \approx N(X) \tilde{I}(t), \quad \nabla I(X, t) \approx \mathbb{B}(X) \tilde{I}(t). \quad (39a)$$

Similarly, the weighting field is interpolated as

$$w(X) \approx N(X) \tilde{w}, \quad \nabla w(X) \approx \mathbb{B}(X) \tilde{w}. \quad (39b)$$

Here, N is the vector of appropriate shape functions, $\mathbb{B} = \nabla N$ is the compatibility matrix, and \tilde{I} and \tilde{w} are the vectors of nodal values of the light intensity and the test function, respectively. In the numerical simulations presented in Section 6 we use three-node isoparametric triangular elements.

Inserting the aforementioned approximations into Eq. (38) gives

$$\bar{\mathbf{w}}^T \int_{B^e} \mathbf{N}^T (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \mathbb{B} \bar{\mathbf{I}} + \sigma \mathbf{N} \bar{\mathbf{I}}) dV = 0, \quad (40)$$

which must hold for any $\bar{\mathbf{w}}$.

The element level residual vector for the light intensity is expressed as

$$\mathbf{R}^I = \int_{B^e} \mathbf{N}^T (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \mathbb{B} \bar{\mathbf{I}} + \sigma \mathbf{N} \bar{\mathbf{I}}) dV, \quad (41)$$

while the tangent matrix reads

$$\mathbb{K} = \int_{B^e} \mathbf{N}^T \boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \mathbb{B} dV + \int_{B^e} \sigma \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{N} dV. \quad (42)$$

Here, the first term on the right-hand side represents the light gradient matrix, whereas the second is the light attenuation matrix.

5.2. Implementation of mass balance equations

The governing mass balance equations introduced in Section 4.5 are treated locally at the integration points. This simplified treatment is possible thanks to our assumption that neglects the diffusivity of photo-initiators and radicals (see also Section 4.5).

The equations are thus numerically integrated using a backward-Euler time discretization scheme. For the sake of generality, and to avoid redundant notation, the general formulation introduced in Section 3 is here adopted. Accordingly, the numerical implementation of the generic mass balance equation reads

$$C_{n+1} - C_n - \sum_{j=1}^r \bar{v}_{C_j, n+1} \Delta t \bar{J}_{j, n+1} = 0, \quad (43)$$

for all governing mass balance equations, where subscripts $n+1$ and n denote the current and previous time step, respectively, and Δt the time step.

The resulting non-linear system is solved through the classical Newton-Raphson iterative method. A tolerance of 10^{-6} for the stopping criterion on the norm of the unknown increment is adopted.

Eq. (43) enables the time-dependent numerical evaluation of all mass balance equations, which in turn allows the determination of the gel fraction (37) at any time instant corresponding to the experimental protocol. Although the gel fraction is defined locally as a spatially-dependent field in Section 4.6, its experimental determination yields a global quantity. The numerically evaluated $XL(X, t)$ is therefore averaged over the sample domain, and the resulting gel fraction at a generic time t_i is evaluated.

6. Results

In this section we first discuss the obtained experimental results; then, we test the validity of the model through several numerical simulations and comparisons with these experimental results. The identification of model parameters will be discussed as well.

6.1. Experimental results

Sample temperature during crosslinking, T_{XL} , was varied between 20 °C and 60 °C, corresponding to temperatures below the crystallization temperature (T_c) or above the melting temperature (T_m) of the material, respectively, to investigate the effect of the polymer's physical state (in the presence or absence of crystalline domains) on crosslinking. Our previous work on the same material [5] demonstrated that at $T_{XL} = 20$ °C, the presence of crystalline domains restricts chain mobility and limits crosslinking, which therefore occurs mainly within the amorphous regions of the PCL chains [28]. This results in a lower overall crosslinking density compared with $T_{XL} = 60$ °C, where the material is fully amorphous and chains are more mobile. Interestingly, the results obtained in this work (Fig. 6) indicate that the gel fraction at

$T_{XL} = 20$ °C was slightly higher than that at 60 °C. This difference can be explained by variations in the degree of crosslinking here achieved during the 3D printing process, most likely due to oxygen inhibition of the crosslinking reaction. Oxygen present in the surrounding air is known to hinder the photo-polymerization of acrylate and methacrylate groups by forming a superficial oxygen inhibition layer (OIL) [29]. At surfaces exposed to air, oxygen readily diffuses into the material and reacts with light-generated radicals, forming less reactive radicals. This process scavenges active radicals and slows or even suppresses the photo-crosslinking reaction. Notably, this inhibitory effect is expected to be more pronounced at $T_{XL} = 60$ °C, likely due to the higher oxygen diffusivity at higher temperatures [30]. It should also be emphasized that all samples in this work were 3D printed, whereas the samples obtained at $T_{XL} = 60$ °C in our previous work [5] were prepared via compression molding and crosslinking between two glass slides, a configuration that likely shielded the material from oxygen diffusion.

As expected, the other two crosslinking parameters, *i.e.*, the UV light intensity ($I_{XL} = 0.5$ or 6 mW/cm²), and the photo-crosslinking time (t_{XL} , in the 2–300 s range), also had a significant impact on the gel fraction. For both T_{XL} values, increasing the t_{XL} led to higher G_F^{exp} . Specifically, for $T_{XL} = 20$ °C (Figs. 6(a) and 6(b)), a plateau G_F^{exp} of ~85% was reached for $I_{XL} = 6$ mW/cm², while for the lower UV light intensity ($I_{XL} = 0.5$ mW/cm²) the G_F^{exp} continued to increase up to 300 s. At $T_{XL} = 60$ °C (Figs. 6(c) and 6(d)), plateau values of ~70% and 50% were instead achieved for $I_{XL} = 6$ and 0.5 mW/cm², respectively. These plateau values were denoted as $G_F^{\text{max}}(T)$ in Section 4.3.1.

6.2. Analysis set-up

The experimental photo-crosslinking process is simulated considering a two-dimensional sample of dimensions $L \times H$ mm, L and H being, respectively specimen length and thickness. The domain is meshed using 2000 finite elements and 1111 nodes. A mesh convergence study was performed to validate mesh discretization. The application of the UV light is simulated by applying the boundary condition (16b) on the upper edge of the domain (see Fig. 7), *i.e.*, $I(X, H, t) = \bar{I}_0$ which is kept constant for all the analysis time interval. Two values of \bar{I}_0 are adopted and they are equal to the experimental ones ($I_{XL} = 0.5$ mW/cm² or 6 mW/cm²). The analysis time interval is assumed equal to the experimental exposure time, t_{XL} , in the 2–300 s range. An adaptive time step Δt between 10^{-8} and 0.01 s was adopted. Fixed time steps (0.5, 0.1, 0.05, 0.01, and 0.001 s) were also adopted to verify the robustness of the implementation.

These tests will be repeated considering two different material states corresponding to the crosslinking temperatures T_{XL} of 20 °C and 60 °C.

6.3. Identification of model parameters

This section is dedicated to parameters calibration for the proposed model, necessary to conduct the analyses described in previous subsection.

A certain number of model parameters are derived from technical data. They include: the specimen length L and thickness H , the saturation limit of the gel fraction G_F^{max} for the various T_{XL} and I_{XL} , the initial molar concentration fields of PH and PCL, and the molar absorptivity of PH, used to evaluate both the extinction field σ (18) and, together with the quantum efficiency of PH and the monochromatic light frequency, the rate constant \bar{k}_{ph} (10b). These parameters are listed in Table 1.

Regarding the remaining parameters to be evaluated, it should be noted that, as stated throughout the manuscript, this complex model aims to minimize the number of arbitrary parameters requiring calibration, particularly due to the lack of experimental evidences. Accordingly, and following the simplified rationale introduced in Section 4.3.1

Fig. 6. Gel fraction (G_F) values obtained for 3D printed PCL specimens as a function of the UV light intensity (I_{XL}) and crosslinking time (t_{XL}) for: (a)–(b) $T_{XL} = 20^\circ\text{C}$ and (c)–(d) $T_{XL} = 60^\circ\text{C}$. Comparison between experimental (EXP) and numerical (FEM) results.

Table 1

Parameters obtained from technical data and/or derived evaluations, as in the case of \tilde{k}_{ph} (10b), $\nu = c \lambda^{-1}$, and the two initial molar concentration fields (5).

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Units
Length of specimen	L	$3.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$	m
Thickness of specimen	H	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$	m
Gel fraction saturation limit ($T_{XL} = 20^\circ\text{C}, I_{XL} = 0.5 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$)	G_F^{max}	0.76	-
Gel fraction saturation limit ($T_{XL} = 20^\circ\text{C}, I_{XL} = 6 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$)	G_F^{max}	0.87	-
Gel fraction saturation limit ($T_{XL} = 60^\circ\text{C}, I_{XL} = 0.5 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$)	G_F^{max}	0.52	-
Gel fraction saturation limit ($T_{XL} = 60^\circ\text{C}, I_{XL} = 6 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$)	G_F^{max}	0.70	-
Molar absorptivity of PH	α_{PH}	8.7	$\text{m}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
Quantum efficiency of PH	ϕ_{PH}	0.5	-
Monochromatic frequency	ν	$8.21 \cdot 10^{14}$	s^{-1}
Radical generation rate constant	\tilde{k}_{ph}	$1.8 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$\text{m}^2 \text{ W}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
Initial concentration of PH	$PH(t=0)$	108.8	mol m^{-3}
Initial concentration of PCL	$PCL(t=0)$	331.3	mol m^{-3}

—based on the mobility of the polymer chains involved in crosslinking reactions and an approximate assessment of their likelihood of interaction — we set

$$\alpha = 0.5, \quad \beta = 2, \quad \gamma = \beta, \quad \delta = 1. \quad (44)$$

Similar reasons drive our choice of the double crosslinking rate factor, $k_{xl}^1(T)$. In the absence of any further experimental data that may help its definition, introducing a function for its evaluation would be unjustified. Accordingly, since k_{xl} corresponds to a four-way directional possibility, while k_{xl}^1 is governed by a one-way directional possibility,

we set

$$k_{xl}^1(T) = 0.25 \tilde{k}_{xl}(T), \quad (45)$$

where we recall that $\tilde{k}_{xl}(T)$ denotes the temperature-dependent maximum value of the single crosslinking rate function (29).

It follows that the only (temperature-dependent) parameters that need to be calibrated are the termination rate k_t , the activation rate k_a , and the parameters defining the single crosslinking rate function (29), namely \tilde{k}_{xl} , P , and Q .

Fig. 7. Applied boundary condition in the numerical simulations of the UV-crosslinking process.

Parameter k_t is calibrated to ensure that the constraints on the radical concentration field (13) are satisfied. Specifically, in accordance with the experimental results on the gel fraction and its saturation limit presented in Section 2, $k_t(T)$ is selected so that the average radical concentration remains within the upper and lower bounds of condition (13) for the two temperatures at which the experiments were conducted. Note that this calibration is intended to provide a representative order of magnitude for $k_t(T)$, rather than a precise value. Accordingly, the knowledge of k_a is not required here, as the consumption of radicals due to the activation reaction (14) is negligible compared to that associated with the termination reaction (11). Although neither the presence of oxygen nor diffusion processes are explicitly modeled, this assumption is physically motivated by the consideration that, at high temperatures, increased chain mobility and polymer microstructure promote oxygen diffusion into the system. This, in turn, reduces the radical concentration field compared to the same process at lower temperatures, where the material is in its semi-crystalline state. A more detailed discussion is provided in Section 7.

Given $k_t(T)$, the activation rate factor $k_a(T)$ and the parameters defining the single-crosslinking rate function (29) — $\tilde{k}_{xl}(T)$, $P(T)$, and $Q(T)$ — are calibrated as follows. For each selected temperature, T_{XL} , the corresponding value of $k_t(T)$ is used. Then, according to the experimental protocol, the incident light intensity \bar{I}_0 is set to 6 mW cm^{-2} . For each combination of temperature and incident intensity, parameters $k_a(T)$, $\tilde{k}_{xl}(T)$, $P(T)$, and $Q(T)$ are calibrated such that:

$$|\overline{\mathcal{G}_F}(t_i) - \mathcal{G}_F^{\text{exp}}(t_i)| \leq \epsilon, \quad (46)$$

where $\overline{\mathcal{G}_F}(t_i)$ denotes the numerically evaluated averaged gel fraction at each time t_i , computed following the procedure described in Section 5.2, $\mathcal{G}_F^{\text{exp}}(t_i)$ is the corresponding experimentally-measured gel fraction values at times t_i (Section 6.1), and ϵ represents the prescribed tolerance.

The resulting parameters are listed in Table 2. Based on the simplified rationale used to define the proportionality of rate factors in single crosslinking reactions — which relies on polymer chain mobility — the activation rate $k_a(T)$ is expected to be lower than $\tilde{k}_{xl}(T)$ for a fixed temperature; therefore, all combinations for which $k_a(T) > \tilde{k}_{xl}(T)$ are discarded. Moreover, given the higher chain mobility in the amorphous state than in the semi-crystalline one, parameters $k_a(T)$ and $\tilde{k}_{xl}(T)$ are expected to be higher for the case where $T_{XL} = 60^\circ\text{C}$.

Finally, the results of the calibration step are reported in Figs. 6(b) and 6(d). The model catches well the experimental results, demonstrating its validity for both the analyzed temperatures and high UV intensity.

6.4. Numerical results and experimental validation

After model calibration, the validation on data related to $I_{XL} = 0.5 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$ follows. The results are reported in Figs. 6(a) and 6(c). Results show an overall very good match with experimental data for exposure times from 60 to 300 s, with relative errors varying from about 4% to 30% for $T_{XL} = 20^\circ\text{C}$ and from 0.3% to 8% for $T_{XL} = 60^\circ\text{C}$. The limited prediction for the lowest $t_{XL}=30$ s may be attributed to various factors such as difficulties in experimental measurements of the gel fraction for low crosslinking densities and the limited time interval for which the light may have not reached totally its intensity. Moreover, for low values of t_{XL} the crosslinking process is in a transient state, that is not described by the model.

Note that the calibration of the aforementioned parameters is not affected by the double crosslinking rate factor, k_{xl}^{xl} , which therefore plays no role in the previous calibration procedure. Instead, k_{xl}^{xl} provides a quantitative description of the photo-crosslinking process. In fact, only the double crosslinked chains contribute to the mechanical behavior of the final sample. Accordingly, we compute the average concentration field, along the sample domain, of chain concentrations $\text{PCL}_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2}}$, $\text{PCL}_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2}}$, $\text{PCL}_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2}}$, $\text{PCL}_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2}}$, $\text{PCL}_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2}}$, and XL for the case $T_{XL} = 20^\circ\text{C}$ and $I_{XL} = 0.5 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$. Results in terms of concentration versus time are reported in Figs. 8(a), 8(b), and 8(c). At the beginning (Fig. 8(b)), i.e., for times lower than 30 s, the main contribution to XL (defined in Eq. (35) and used to compute the gel fraction (37)) is given by $\text{PCL}_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2}}$. As it can be observed from Fig. 8(a), as time increases, $\text{PCL}_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ gives the main contribution to XL . Chain types $\text{PCL}_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2}}$, $\text{PCL}_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2}}$, and $\text{PCL}_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ give the lowest contributions to the gel fraction (Fig. 8(c)). The model is thus able to give insights on the contribution of the different species involved to the crosslinking extent.

7. Discussion and outlook

Within the proposed model, and in view of the limited experimental information available, we adopted a simplified yet physically-grounded description of the photo-crosslinking process.

The first approximation, introduced in Section 4.2, concerns the radical termination mechanism, here represented by the single reaction (11), although it may occur through multiple pathways. Termination can result from radical-radical interactions ($n, R \cdot \rightarrow n, R$) or reactions with oxygen ($R \cdot + O_2 \rightarrow R$). Accounting for oxygen effects would require modeling its temperature-dependent diffusivity and reaction kinetics—both presently unknown. Such an extension could qualitatively explain the lower values of the gel fraction at higher temperatures, since higher chain mobility should favor crosslinking, but it would also introduce unnecessary complexity and poorly constrained parameters. These additional mechanisms are therefore excluded from the present formulation, though they represent potential extensions if supported by targeted experiments. In this context, the effective role of oxygen is implicitly captured through the termination rate, which controls the radical concentration level. As a result, explicitly introducing oxygen as an additional species would mainly affect the initiation and radical balance, without propagating to the crosslinking kinetics. Consequently, the predictive capability of the model with respect to the quantities of interest remains unchanged.

The second approximation concerns the use of the Beer-Lambert law (16) and the simplified extinction field σ (18). A complete treatment of radiative transfer is given by Alkhoury and Chester [9]

$$\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial I}{\partial t} + \mathbf{\Omega} \cdot \nabla I - j_\nu + \sigma_\nu I + \sigma_{sv} I - \frac{\sigma_{sv}}{4\pi} \int_{4\pi} I \Phi_{sv} d\omega = 0, \quad (47)$$

for any frequency ν , where the radiative intensity I passes through a surface with normal $\mathbf{\Omega}$ and solid angle ω . Here, j_ν is the emission coefficient, σ_ν and σ_{sv} are the absorption and scattering coefficients (whose sum defines the extinction field, $\sigma = \sigma_\nu + \sigma_{sv}$), and Φ_{sv} is the scattering phase function. In most engineering contexts, however, light

Table 2Calibrated rate factor parameters obtained by the numerical model, with the exception of k_{xl}^{xl} , which has been estimated by approximation (31).

Parameter	Symbol	$T_{XL} = 20^\circ\text{C}$	$T_{XL} = 60^\circ\text{C}$	Units
		Value	Value	
Termination rate	k_t	1000	10 000	s^{-1}
Activation rate	k_a	1.92	5.53	s^{-1}
Crosslinking rate constant	\bar{k}_{xl}	2.29	8.7	$\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
Exponential model parameter	P	2	2	$\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
Exponential model parameter	Q	3	2.5	$\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
Double crosslinking rate	k_{xl}^{xl}	0.5725	2.1750	$\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$

Fig. 8. Numerical results in terms of chain concentration versus time for the case $T_{XL} = 20^\circ\text{C}$ and $I_{XL} = 0.5 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$. Concentration types PCL_{\ddagger} , PCL_{\ddagger} , $\text{PCL}_{\ddagger}^{\ddagger}$, $\text{PCL}_{\ddagger}^{\ddagger}$, $\text{PCL}_{\ddagger}^{\ddagger}$, and XL are considered. (a) Results for the total time of 300 s; (b) zoom of the results for 30 s; (c) zoom of the contribution of PCL_{\ddagger} , PCL_{\ddagger} , and $\text{PCL}_{\ddagger}^{\ddagger}$.

transmission occurs much faster than the characteristic process times, and scattering and emission can be neglected, as commonly done in solid mechanics [8,9,31]. Under these assumptions, Eq. (47) reduces to the Beer–Lambert law. Scattering effects — potentially relevant in the semi-crystalline state — would require dedicated experiments to determine σ_{sv} and Φ_{sv} , while the steady-state assumption remains appropriate. Accordingly, in the present formulation the extinction field is introduced in an effective sense and is practically reduced to an absorption-dominated contribution due to the lack of experimental data required to characterize scattering. It is acknowledged that crystalline domains may induce light scattering and local heterogeneities by excluding photoinitiators and radicals. However, such effects primarily influence the photoinitiation stage. Within the range of radical concentrations considered, the system is governed by termination kinetics, which rapidly damp local variations. As a consequence, explicitly accounting for these effects would not affect the overall crosslinking

kinetics or the resulting network formation. Therefore, while a more detailed heterogeneous description could be introduced, its impact on the model predictions would be negligible within the present framework.

An additional simplification adopted in this work concerns the estimation of rate factors, specifically the function (29) and the proportional factors defined with respect to it, as discussed in Section 4.3.1. In principle, a more physically-based description of temperature-dependent rate factors could rely, for instance, on the [32] law, on the transition state theory [33,34], or on functions derived from these well-established approaches. Such formulations would require knowledge of the activation energy or of the activation Gibbs free energy.

Still regarding the rate factors, a rough approximation was adopted for k_{xl}^{xl} (31). However, since the available experimental data are limited to the gel fraction, which is not directly related to k_{xl}^{xl} , it is preferable to keep the number of parameters to a minimum and to base the model on the available experimental evidence. In general, each additional

parameter would require dedicated experiments for proper calibration; otherwise, the model would only reproduce the data without providing meaningful physical insight. Mechanical tests on samples with different gel fractions could, in principle, help to infer information on k_{xl}^{xl} .

As stated in Section 4.3, under condition (13) on the radical concentration field, some chemical reactions — and the corresponding chemical species — can be reasonably neglected. For instance, although it is theoretically possible for two radicals to activate both terminals of a chain, forming a species such as $PCL_{\ddot{\cdot}}$, or to react with the inactive ends of crosslinked chains of type $PCL_{\ddot{\cdot}}$ or $PCL_{\ddot{\cdot}}$, as well as for two $PCL_{\ddot{\cdot}}$ chains to react with each other, these events are expected to be extremely rare. Introducing such additional species or reactions would only increase the number of mass balance equations and rate factors, thereby requiring more parameters to calibrate without improving model fidelity. Given condition (13), we believe that the present formulation already captures all chemically relevant processes, and the omission of these secondary reactions is fully justified.

We conclude this discussion by emphasizing that, while the model has been developed for radical photocrosslinking of methacrylate-based systems and validated on methacrylated poly(ϵ -caprolactone), its structure is sufficiently general to be adapted to other polymer systems. Specifically, the applicability of the proposed model to different polymer systems primarily depends on the activation mechanism and, subsequently, on the crosslinking chemistry.

With respect to the activation mechanism, the present formulation adopts a photo-induced trigger; alternative systems employing a different kind of trigger would only require the replacement of the light-induced chemistry. As an example, the use of thermal initiators which generate active radicals through temperature would require the replacement with an appropriate thermal activation law. This concerns the light propagation law (16), the reaction governing radical generation, *i.e.*, the photoinitiator dissociation (9), and the definition of k_{ph} . Since the subsequent evolution is controlled by the concentration of active radicals, the overall framework remains unchanged once these quantities are defined. In other words, the photo-chemistry could, in principle, be reformulated or even replaced by prescribing a given concentration of active radicals (or other reactive species), without affecting the core structure of the model or the resulting predictions.

Conversely, the crosslinking chemistry is inherently system-dependent. The formulation in Section 4.3 as well as the polymeric configurations illustrated in Figs. 4 and 5 reflect the specific network structure of the material under investigation. On the one hand, it is expected that the formulation can be directly applicable to polymers systems that share the following conditions: (i) radical photocrosslinking mechanism, initiated by light in the presence of a suitable photoinitiator; (ii) presence of (meth)acrylate functional groups (*e.g.*, acrylates, methacrylates). Under these conditions, the model can be applied (directly or with minor modifications) to other semi-crystalline polymers, such as methacrylated polylactic acid or polyethylene glycol, which exhibit similar crosslinking mechanisms, and to other polymer networks built from linear or branched precursors or employing different photo-initiators enabling crosslinking under different irradiation wavelengths. On the other hand, while the light transport formulation is general, for systems exhibiting different network topologies, the corresponding reaction scheme would need to be adapted, although the overall modeling strategy remains general. As an example, extensions to other photo-crosslinkable systems, such as thiol-ene, would require appropriate modifications of the underlying reaction scheme. Such adjustments would not pose significant challenges, and the proposed framework is readily adaptable to these alternative polymeric systems.

Finally, the model is calibrated using the gel fraction — currently, the only experimental data available to estimate the crosslinking efficiency — leading to an empirical formulation of the crosslinking rate (Eq. (29)). The adoption of a different experimental target

would modify this functional relationship, without affecting the overall structure of the model.

8. Conclusions

The present work has presented a theoretical tool to support the rationale and optimization of radical photo-crosslinking in semi-crystalline polymer networks, which is particularly valuable considering the complexity and the high time for experimentation of these materials.

The model has combined a three-dimensional formulation of the Beer–Lambert law for radiative transfer with mass balance equations governing photo-initiator activation, radical generation, and crosslinking reactions. Reaction kinetics are described through the law of mass action, enabling a quantitative prediction of network evolution as a function of processing parameters. The framework has been applied to poly(ϵ -caprolactone)-based networks, demonstrating the potential of the approach in predicting the experimentally measured values of the gel fraction, a physical quantity directly connected to the extent of crosslinking. Model results have been also validated on different crosslinking conditions, involving different exposure times, temperatures, and light intensities. The results have demonstrated a very good performance of the model in predicting the experimental measurements of the gel fraction. The identification of model parameters has been discussed in detail and conducted by applying certain simplifications to the formulation.

As a future extension, it is recommended to collect more experimental data useful for a more physically-grounded derivation of parameters. The formulation establishes a foundation for future coupling with thermo-mechanical and shape memory constitutive models, with implications for the design of high-performance polymer systems. Along this direction, other quantities, such as the crosslinking density obtained via mechanical testing, can be used for further model validation in coupled physics. Ultimately, despite its application and validation on poly(ϵ -caprolactone)-based semi-crystalline networks, the formulation is general and applicable to other polymer networks built by means of photo-induced radical crosslinking of methacrylate functionalized endgroups. Extension to other photo-crosslinkable systems and trigger mechanisms will be the object of future work.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Matteo Arricca: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Lorenzo Bonetti:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Massimo Messori:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Stefano Pandini:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation. **Giulia Scalet:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

Valuable discussions with Prof. Maurizio Toselli (University of Bologna) are acknowledged. This work was funded by the European Union ERC CoDe4Bio Grant ID 101039467. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council.

Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Funded by
the European Union

European Research Council
Established by the European Commission

Data availability

Data generated in this study have been deposited in the Zenodo database at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20340108>.

References

- [1] S. Moon, H. Hwang, H. Jeon, S. Park, Y.Y. I.S. Bae, Photocrosslinkable natural polymers in tissue engineering, *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* 11 (2023) 1127757.
- [2] H. Masai, T. Nakagawa, J. Terao, Recent progress in photoreactive crosslinkers in polymer network materials toward advanced photocontrollability, *Polym. J.* 56 (2024) 297–307.
- [3] G. Scalet, Two-way and multiple-way shape memory polymers for soft robotics: An overview, *Actuators* 9 (1) (2020) 10.
- [4] F. Friess, C. Wischke, M. Behl, A. Lendlein, Oligo(epsilon-caprolactone)-based polymer networks prepared by photocrosslinking in solution, *J. Appl. Biomater. Funct. Mater.* 10 (2012) 273–279.
- [5] L. Bonetti, D. Natali, S. Pandini, M. Messori, M. Toselli, G. Scalet, Tailoring the shape-memory performance of 2D and 3D fabricated semi-crystalline PCL networks via optimal crosslinking, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* 47 (2) (2026) e00631.
- [6] K.N. Long, T.F. Scott, H.J. Qi, C.N. Bowman, M.L. Dunn, Photomechanics of light-activated polymers, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 57 (2009) 1103–1121.
- [7] R. Long, H.J. Qi, M.L. Dunn, Thermodynamics and mechanics of photochemically reacting polymers, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 61 (2013) 2212–2239.
- [8] C.M. Hamel, F. Cui, S.A. Chester, A finite element method for light activated shape-memory polymers, *Int. J. Numer. Meth. Eng.* 111 (2017) 447–473.
- [9] K. Alkhoury, S.A. Chester, A chemo-thermo-mechanically coupled theory of photo-reacting polymers: Application to modeling photo-degradation with irradiation-driven heat transfer, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 197 (2025) 106050.
- [10] E. Andrzejewska, Photopolymerization kinetics of multifunctional monomers, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* 26 (2001) 605–665.
- [11] G. Odian, Principles of Polymerization, fourth ed., Wiley-Interscience, Hoboken, N.J., 2004.
- [12] P.C. Hiemenz, T.P. Lodge, Polymer Chemistry, second ed., CRC Press - Taylor and Francis Group, 2007.
- [13] J. Wu, Z. Zhao, X. Hamel, X. Kuang, Z. Guo, H.J. Qi, Evolution of material properties during free radical photopolymerization, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 112 (2018) 25–49.
- [14] R. Brighenti, M.P. Cosma, L. Marsavina, A. Spagnoli, M. Terzano, Multiphysics modelling of the mechanical properties in polymers obtained via photo-induced polymerization, *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Tech.* 117 (1) (2021) 481–499.
- [15] R. Brighenti, M.P. Cosma, S. Monchetti, Mechanics of polymers obtained by layered photopolymerization, *Eur. J. Mech. A-Solid* 106 (2024) 105323.
- [16] H. Zhu, Y. Guo, Z. Chen, S. Qu, A photo-chemo-mechanical coupling constitutive model for photopolymerization-based 3D printing hydrogels, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 192 (2024) 105830.
- [17] C.D. Wick, A.J. Peters, G. Li, Simulation study of shape memory polymer networks formed by free radical polymerization, *Polymer* 281 (2023) 126114.
- [18] S. Lazzari, G. Storti, Modeling multiradicals in crosslinking MMA/EGDMA bulk copolymerization, *Macromol. Theory Simulations* 23 (1) (2014) 15–35.
- [19] P. Roose, H. Van den Bergen, A. Houben, D. Bontinck, S. Van Vlierberghe, A semiempirical scaling model for the solid- and liquid-state photopolymerization kinetics of semicrystalline acrylated oligomers, *Macromolecules* 51 (14) (2018) 5027–5038.
- [20] P. Roose, E. Vermoesen, S. Van Vlierberghe, Non-steady scaling model for the kinetics of the photo-induced free radical polymerization of crosslinking networks, *Polym. Chem.* 11 (2020) 2475–2484.
- [21] M. Arricca, N. Inverardi, S. Pandini, M. Toselli, M. Messori, F. Auricchio, G. Scalet, Phenomenological modeling of the stress-free two-way shape-memory effect in semi-crystalline networks: Formulation, numerical simulation, and experimental validation, *Eur. J. Mech. A-Solid* 105 (2024) 105245.
- [22] M. Arricca, N. Inverardi, S. Pandini, M. Toselli, M. Messori, G. Scalet, Finite strain continuum phenomenological model describing the shape-memory effects in multi-phase semi-crystalline networks, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 195 (2025) 105955.
- [23] N. Inverardi, M. Toselli, G. Scalet, M. Messori, F. Auricchio, S. Pandini, Stress-free two-way shape memory effect of poly(ethylene glycol)/poly(epsilon-caprolactone) semicrystalline networks, *Macromolecules* 55 (19) (2022) 8533–8547.
- [24] M. Messori, M.D. Esposti, K. Paderni, S. Pandini, T.R. Simone Passera, M. Toselli, Chemical and thermomechanical tailoring of the shape memory effect in poly(epsilon-caprolactone)-based systems, *J. Mater. Sci.* 48 (2013) 424–440.
- [25] L. Bonetti, D. Natali, S. Pandini, M. Messori, M. Toselli, G. Scalet, 4D printing of semi-crystalline crosslinked polymer networks with two-way shape-memory effect, *Mater. Des.* 238 (2024) 112725.
- [26] S.R. De Groot, P. Mazur, Non-Equilibrium Thermodynamics, Dover, 1984.
- [27] A.B. Davis, A. Marshak, Photon propagation in heterogeneous optical media with spatial correlations: enhanced mean-free-paths and wider-than-exponential free-path distributions, *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiant. Transfer* 84 (2004) 3–34.
- [28] I. Razquin, A. Iregui, M. Cobos, J. Latasa, A. Eceiza, K. González, L. Martin, A. Müller, A. González, L. Irusta, Cationically photocured epoxy/polycaprolactone materials processed by solution electrospinning, melt electrowriting and 3D printing: Morphology and shape memory properties, *Polymer* 282 (2023) 126160.
- [29] K. Studer, C. Decker, E. Beck, R. Schwalm, Overcoming oxygen inhibition in UV-curing of acrylate coatings by carbon dioxide inerting, part i, *Prog. Org. Coatings* 48 (1) (2003) 92–100.
- [30] M.C. Celina, A. Quintana, Oxygen diffusivity and permeation through polymers at elevated temperature, *Polymer* 150 (2018) 326–342.
- [31] H. Zhang, Y. Hu, A constitutive model that couples light propagation direction and deformation for photo-responsive polymers and polymeric gels, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 191 (2024) 105786.
- [32] S. Arrhenius, Über die reaktionsgeschwindigkeit bei der inversion von rohrzucker durch säuren, *Z. Phys. Chem.* 4 (1889) 226–248.
- [33] H. Eyring, The activated complex in chemical reactions, *J. Chem. Phys.* 3 (1935) 107–115.
- [34] M.G. Evans, M. Polanyi, Some applications of the transition state method to the calculation of reaction velocities, especially in solution, *Trans. Faraday Soc.* 31 (1935) 875–894.